

REHABILITATION OF MAXILLARY DEFECT WITH AN DEFINITIVE OBTURATOR- A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Maxillofacial abnormalities are anomalies or malformations in the facial bones and/or soft tissues. Oral cancer treatment often involves surgical resection. Maxillectomy, or maxillofacial resection, substantially impairs speech and deglutition capabilities. An individual's behavior in society is influenced by their altered oral and facial structures.

KEYWORDS: Definitive prosthesis, interim prosthesis, maxillary defects, maxillary obturator, oral cancer, surgical obturator

I. INTRODUCTION

Orthoantral communication defects can cause difficulty with eating and swallowing, slurred speech, and facial disfigurement when a maxillectomy is performed. The prosthodontist plays a vital role in rehabilitating these defects with an obturator. Since it forms a wall between the nasal and oral cavities, prosthetic rehabilitation of these intraoral maxillary abnormalities is crucial.

A maxillofacial prosthesis, as defined by GPT 9, is any prosthesis intended to replace a portion of either cranial or stomatognathic component.

An obturator is a maxillofacial prosthesis that is utilized to repair a tissue opening, congenital or acquired, predominantly of the hard palate and/or adjacent alveolar or soft tissue structures (GPT 9). Using an obturator to reconstruct the maxillectomy defect has a number of benefits. In addition to restoring the soft and hard tissues that have been lost, it creates a barrier between the nasal and oral cavities and allows the patient to swallow, masticate, and speak nearly normally. Maxillectomy patients are rehabilitated with different obturators at regular intervals. Following surgery, surgical obturators are administered to preserve function while the tissues heal. Due to the increased anesthetic and surgical time required for adjustments, some surgeons avoid immediate obturators. Surgical obturators can be immediate or delayed surgical obturators.³ The continually shifting tissues and delicate areas benefit from the proper healing provided by interim obturators. Most often, interim obturators are administered 7–10 days following surgery. After six months of surgery, definitive prostheses are administered, pending full tissue recovery. A multidisciplinary strategy is necessary for the treatment of individuals with malignant tumors in the maxilla, involving radiotherapy, surgery, physical therapy, and prosthetic

appliances. With a modified obturator, patients with palatal abnormalities can regain oral function with a maxillary full denture. The patient's aptitude and prior denture-wearing experience may have played a significant role in the outcome of their care⁵. Nonetheless, every patient is distinct and has different issues that require individualized care. The methodical process for creating a closed, lightweight acrylic obturator for a maxillectomy patient is outlined in this clinical report.

II. CASE REPORT

A 58-year-old male patient was referred to a dental clinic for a reconstructive prosthesis for a hemi maxillectomy defect. His chief complaint was difficulty eating and speaking, with liquid coming out of the nose during intake due to missing teeth in the upper front and back regions of the jaw. The patient seemed to be doing okay, but he had trouble drinking water and swallowing food, so he wasn't happy with the meals. Hypernasal speech was clearly audible due to oral and nasal communication. Six months prior, the patient disclosed a medical history that included the surgical excision of a well-differentiated squamous cell carcinoma lesion on the right maxilla. There was psychological trauma affecting the patient. The extraoral appearance of the patient was found to be asymmetrical with a depressed right malar region. Upon intraoral inspection, a well-healed surgical defect involving a portion of the alveolar ridge, maxillary tuberosity, and hard palate in the maxilla was discovered, resulting in an oroantral connection. Teeth missing: 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17 On the left side of the maxillary arch, there were intact teeth ranging from the central incisor to the second molar. The maxilla was removed through the midline, indicating a Class I deformity, according to Armany. The resection site was sore, sensitive, and slightly inflamed. The patient was apprised of all of the pros and cons of this prosthesis, and agreement was obtained. Following a thorough examination, the surgical site's undercuts were blocked with gauze soaked in betadine solution to avoid causing extra damage to the healing tissues.

III. PROCEDURE

With the use of perforated stock trays, the initial impression was created using Alginate (Prime Dental Products Pvt. Ltd.), an irreversible hydrocolloid impression medium. The impression was poured using Type III dental stone (kalastone, Kalabhai Ltd., Mumbai, India). On the cast, the obturator's expansion was noted. A specially designed tray was created to create a second impression. Border molding for recording the sulcus area was done with a low-fusing impression compound, and the defect area was recorded with a medium-fusing impression compound. Secondary/final wash impression with heavy body addition silicon impression material, followed by wash impression with light body rubber base impression material. Possible treatment options for prosthetics were explained to the patient as follows: removable prosthesis. Obturator-Acrylic (heat-cured acrylic denture base resin material), cast partial denture Hollow bulb obturator connected to partial denture with magnet, fixed prosthesis Implant-retained maxillary obturator, zygomatic, or pterygoid implants. Due to financial constraints, the patient opted for a removable

obturator with acrylic (heat-cured denture base resin) as the material. The obturator was planned with a C clasp and retentive tags. The clasps were made of 22-gauge circular stainless steel wire and fitted into the retentive portion of the teeth on the non-resected side. Modeling wax was utilized to block the damaged area, and the palatal shape was curved. Acrylic resin was used in the conventional fabrication process. Flasking was completed for the invested cast. Dewaxing was done. Acrylic resin was used to pack the materials, which were then cured. The retrieved prosthesis was thoroughly finished and polished to prevent discomfort. The completed prosthesis was fitted and tested for border extension. The patient was requested to drink water and consume food in order to test the prosthesis's peripheral seal, evaluate water leakage from the nose, and assess food accumulation from the nose. The patient was also engaged in a regular conversation to assess for hypernasality. The patient was taught how to remove and place the obturator, followed by instructions on care and hygiene. A nighttime removal of the prosthesis was proposed. The patient was educated about all of the obturator's advantages and disadvantages.

IV. DISCUSSION

After a maxillectomy, an occlusor prosthesis is necessary to restore oral function. Basic prosthodontic principles, such as stress distribution throughout the arch, arch stabilization with a rigid major connector, and component retention and stabilization at specific arch locations to reduce dislodging functional forces, should guide the design of removable obturator prostheses. Compared to patients with acquired mandibular abnormalities, patients with acquired maxillary defects are easier to rehabilitate, and after treatment, pleasant, satisfactory outcomes are easily noticeable. Construction of the definitive obturator should wait until the defect location has fully healed. Depending on the tumor's prognosis, the defects size, the rate of healing, and the existence of teeth, it could take three to six months following surgery (8–10). Patients with maxillary deformities would undoubtedly have a better quality of life with an obturator that is properly built. With the use of a prosthetic obturator, it is possible to restore speech, resonance, mastication, swallowing, and aesthetic abilities, particularly those related to the midface.

V. CONCLUSION

Oral cancers are frequently found and have a propensity to spread quickly; therapy must be started right away to stop the cancer from spreading. An interdisciplinary approach is required to repair the functions of the mouth that were damaged during surgery. The sealing of the opening between the nasal and oral cavities is made possible by the obturator, which stops water from escaping the nose. This aids the patient in receiving food and liquids orally without regurgitating. The patient may now feed themselves without a Ryle's tube. Additionally, the prosthesis can be completed chair side and is less intrusive.

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Figure1: Intraoral defect (Aramany class I defect)

Figure 2: Frontal view of defect

Figure 3: After filling the defect with gauge Preliminary impression with irreversible hydrocolloid impression material was made

Figure 4: Custom tray was fabricated for making secondary impression

Figure 5: Border molding for sulcus area was recorded with low fusing impression compound and the defect area was recorded with medium fusing impression compound

Figure 6: Secondary /final wash impression was made with rubber base addition silicone impression material

Figure 7: Block out of defect on cast with modeling wax

Figure 8: Try in of wax up prosthesis in patients' mouth

Figure 9: Posterior Wax up Occlusion View

Figure 10: Occlusal view of hollow bulb

Figure 11:Pre-operative view

Figure 12:Post-operative view

Figure 13: Happy patient